

Os^{VI} complex with TDSA: For the Os^{VI} complex, the present study indicates that the starting material Os^{VIII} gets reduced to Os^{VI} in the alkaline medium and Os^{VI} formed then complexes with the ligand. The Os^{VI}-TDSA complex was found to be diamagnetic in marked contrast to the expected paramagnetism for a d²-system. The diamagnetism of Os^{VI} complex could be explained to be due to the (—COO⁻)₂(O=Os^{VI}=O)(OH⁻)₂ octahedron, which was brought about by the strongly π -donating oxide groups and was sufficient to cause spin-pairing of the t_{2g} electrons in the lower- d_{xy} level⁶. Such a geometry of the Os^{VI} complex was further supported by the reflectance spectrum, which showed three bands at 13.15 kK and 14.28 kK corresponding to the spin-allowed d-d bands and as a charge transfer band at 40.81 kK^{7,8}.

Thermogravimetric data of the Os^{VI}-TDSA complex showed initial weight loss at 120° corresponding to the loss of five moles of water per mole of the complex.

Acknowledgement

The authors are grateful to Evans Chemetics Inc., (U.S.A.) for a gift sample of thiodisuccinic acid, and to Prof. W. Rahman, for providing facilities, and to U.G.C., New Delhi, for providing financial assistance to one of them (D.S.), and to C.S.I.R., New Delhi, for the award of a Senior Research Fellowship to the other (D.P.S.R.).

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Nephelauxetic and Hypersensitive Nature of Neodymium(III) Complexes with α -Pyridylthiosemicarbazide and its Furfural-2-aldehyde and Thiophene-2-aldehyde Derivatives

C. L. JAIN* and P. N. MUNDLEY

Department of Chemistry, M. M. H. College, Ghazlabad-201 001 and

B. L. KHANDELWAL

Department of Chemistry, Indian Institute of Technology, New Delhi-110 029

Manuscript received 1 March 1984, revised 22 November 1984, accepted 3 June 1985

A new series of octahedral Nd^{III} complexes with recently synthesised α -pyridylthiosemicarbazide (C₆H₈N₄S or 'PT'), *N*-(α -pyridyl)furfural-2-al-

dehyde-thiosemicarbazone (C₁₁H₁₀N₄SO or 'PFT') and *N*-(α -pyridyl)thiophene-2-aldehyde-thiosemicarbazone (C₁₁H₁₀N₄S₂ or 'PTT'), have been isolated and characterised on the basis of their elemental analysis, magnetic and reflectance and ir spectral data revealing 'PT' as bidentate (pyridinic-N and thioketo-S) and 'PFT' and 'PTT' as tetradentate with pyridinic-N, thioketo-S, imine-N and furfuryl-O/thiophenyl-S as donor sites. In the present communication, we report the isolation and characterisation of Nd^{III} complexes with 'PT', 'PFT' and 'PTT' and their nephelauxetic and hypersensitive nature are studied in order to evaluate the stereochemistry of the ligands around Nd^{III} ion.

Experimental

Chemically pure rare earth chloride/nitrate/perchlorate and AnalaR grade chemicals were used throughout. The magnetic susceptibility measurements, reflectance spectra (using MgO as reference), ir spectra (KBr) and far-ir spectra (with CsBr prism using nujol) were recorded as described earlier¹. Elemental analysis for all the present Nd^{III} complexes are found in good agreement with the calculated values, revealing M-L stoichiometric ratio 1:2 (with 'PT') and 1:1 (with 'PFT' and 'PTT'). Nd^{III} ions were estimated by oxalate-formation method². Elemental, magnetic and important ir data are recorded in Table 1, while reflectance spectral bands (cm⁻¹) and relevant parameters in Table 2.

Preparation and isolation of complexes: The ethanolic solution of neodymium hexahydrate trichloride/trinitrate/triperchlorate (10 mmol) were mixed with the refluxing solution of ligand 'PT' (20 mmol) or 'PFT'/'PTT' (10 mmol) in the same solvent. Macrocrystalline and substantially pure products were obtained after refluxing the reaction mixture on a steam-bath for ~40 min (pH 3.5-4.5), which were filtered and then washed successively with ethanol, acetonitrile and finally with small increments of acetone to remove impurities of unreacted ligand and metal ion. All of the complexes were dried completely under vacuum at room temperature and are found insoluble in most of the common organic solvents, viz. DMSO, DMF, dioxane, nitromethane and nitrobenzene, which precluded conductivity measurements and in visible region, reflectance spectra could be undertaken. The presence of ionic chloride/nitrate ions outside the coordination sphere of the complexes were tested by alcoholic AgNO₃ and copper turnings, respectively.

Results and Discussion

Magnetic studies: The values of magnetic moment observed (3.40-3.56 B.M.) for present Nd^{III} complexes having ⁴I_{9/2} ground state term, are closer to those for complexed and free ions as reported by Sinha³ as well as Van Vleck and Frank value⁴ (3.68 B.M.), suggesting octahedral crystal field around the metal ion. A relatively small

TABLE 1—ANALYTICAL, PHYSICAL AND IR SPECTRAL DATA OF Nd^{III} COMPLEXES

Sl. no.	Compd.	Colour	Analysis % : Found/(Calcd.)				μ_{eff} at 302 ± 2 K B.M.	Ir band (cm ⁻¹) and assignment			
			C	S	N*/Cl	H*/Cl		ν_{C-S} + ν_{C-N} of Py. ring	Py. ring breath. modes	ν_{C-S}	Furan*/Thiophene moiety
1.	C ₆ H ₈ N ₄ S (PT)	—	43.6 (42.8)	18.7 (19.1)	28.8* (28.3)*	4.7* (4.6)*	—	1 550s 1 516s	1 086s 973bs	760vs	—
2.	(C ₁₁ H ₁₀ N ₄ SO) (PFT)	—	55.42 (55.66)	13.54 (13.01)	22.25* (22.76)*	4.17* (4.06)*	—	1 590vs 1 560vs	1 085m 1 075sh	825s 810s	610s* 595s*
3.	(C ₁₁ H ₁₀ N ₄ S ₂) (PTT)	—	50.58 (50.88)	24.62 (24.42)	21.05* (21.37)*	3.72* (3.82)*	—	1 540s 1 500sh	1 085s 1 070m	835s 820s	640vs 572vs
4.	[Nd(PT) ₂ Cl ₂].Cl	Cream-white	24.10 (24.57)	10.49 (10.92)	17.68 (18.08)	24.03 (24.57)	3.55	1 570s 1 510sh	1 042s 1 010m	720s 710m	— —
5.	[Nd.PFT]Cl ₂ .Cl	Cream-white	26.57 (26.23)	6.44 (6.82)	21.44 (21.13)	29.04 (28.81)	3.53	1 610m 1 590ms	1 050m 1 025m	770s 745m	575m* 540m*
6.	[Nd(PFT)(NO ₂) ₂ .NO ₂ .2H ₂ O	Light blue	21.56 (21.91)	5.22 (5.57)	16.00* (16.36)*	23.56 (23.11)	3.40	1 610m 1 558ms	1 060m 1 045w	765s 745m	575m* 545m*
7.	[Nd(PTT)(ClO ₄) ₂].ClO ₄	Light pink	18.73 (18.51)	9.08 (9.31)	—	20.46 (20.72)	3.56	1 565s 1 525ms	1 075m 1 050s	785s 740ms	617m 525m

s=Sharp, sbr=sharp broad, ms=medium sharp, vs=very sharp, w=weak.

TABLE 2—ELECTRONIC SPECTRAL (REFLECTANCE) BANDS (cm⁻¹) AND RELEVANT PARAMETERS OF Nd^{III} COMPLEXES

Band assignment and parameter	[Nd(H ₂ O) ₉].Cl ₃	Compound (as Sl. no. in Table 1)			
		4	5	6	7
$^4I_{9/2} \rightarrow ^4F_{3/2}$	11 556	11 540	11 560	11 500	11 350
$\rightarrow ^4F_{5/2}$	12 476	12 470	12 470	12 420	12 530
$\rightarrow ^4F_{7/2}$	13 854	13 470	13 320	13 270	13 250
$\rightarrow ^4F_{9/2}$	14 730	14 700	14 560	14 700	14 710
$\rightarrow (^4G_{5/2}, ^2G_{7/2})$	17 280	17 210	17 100	17 100	17 050
$\rightarrow ^4G_{7/2}$	18 800	18 750	18 850	18 860	18 760
$\rightarrow ^4G_{9/2}$	19 440	19 230	19 300	19 400	19 450
$\rightarrow ^3D_{3/2}$	21 330	21 250	21 250	21 250	21 300
$\rightarrow ^4G_{11/2}$	21 900	21 900	21 800	21 850	21 780
$\rightarrow ^3P_{1/2}$	23 390	23 380	23 360	23 380	23 350
$^* \beta (^4G_{5/2})$	—	0.995 9	0.989 5	0.989 5	0.986 6
$^* \beta (^2P_{1/2})$	—	0.999 5	0.998 7	0.999 5	0.998 2
$\delta (\%)$	—	0.411 0	1.061 1	0.411 0	1.358 1
$b^{1/2}$	—	0.045 2	0.072 4	0.045 27	0.081 5
η	—	0.002 10	0.005 32	0.002 10	0.005 38

* Taken for calculation of $\delta (\%)$, $b^{1/2}$ and η .

difference between observed and Van Vleck and Frank values are considered⁸ most probably due to either minor or no involvement of the metal 4f-orbitals in the bonding. The observed magnetic moment values are also found quite in good agreement with the values reported⁵ for neodymium(III) sulphate, which suggest that Nd^{III} ion in the present complexes act approximately as a free-ion so far as f-electrons are concerned.

Reflectance spectra: In reflectance spectra of Nd^{III} complexes with 'PT', 'PFT' and 'PTT', the assignment of bands to different transitions⁵ are based on comparison with those observed from reflectance of Nd(H₂O)₉.Cl₃, because it would be risky to transfer conclusions from solution measurements to solid measurements⁶. In the present Nd^{III} complexes, a small shift to lower frequencies is observed for all the bands. This red-shift is called

the nephelauxetic shift and has been related to covalency in metal—ligand bond.

The hypersensitive transition observed at 17 280 cm⁻¹ (aquo-metal ion) shows a slight decrease in frequencies by 70–80 cm⁻¹ on complexation (Table 2), where the intensity increases from ϵ 6.06 in the salt upto ϵ 17.10 in the present complexes. This transition is tentatively assigned to $^4I_{9/2} \rightarrow ^4G_{5/2}, ^2G_{7/2}$, because it was not possible to resolve and distinguish the transitions $^4I_{9/2} \rightarrow ^4G_{5/2}$ and $^4I_{9/2} \rightarrow ^2G_{7/2}$. For the hypersensitive transition, this slight red-shift on complexation, clearly indicates^{3,5} that metal-4f and ligand orbitals participate a little in bonding. The band observed in the region 23 360–23 380 cm⁻¹ in the Nd^{III} complexes is assigned⁷ to Stark-level transition $^4I_{9/2} \rightarrow ^3P_{1/2}$. On complexation, the slight red-shift in hypersensitive transition ($^4I_{9/2} \rightarrow ^4G_{5/2}, ^2G_{7/2}$) and

Stark transition (${}^4I_{9/2} \rightarrow {}^3P_{1/2}$) may also be attributed⁷ to the presence of strong donor sites in the ligands 'PT', 'PFT' and 'PTT'.

Parameter of bonding ($b^{1/2}$) which measures the amount of metal-4f and ligand orbital mixing, and covalency-angular overlap parameter (η) which is also related to nephelauxetic ratio (β), are calculated by using the relations^{7,8},

$$\beta = \frac{\bar{\nu}_{\text{complex}}^{\circ}}{\bar{\nu}_{\text{aquo}}^{\circ}}$$

$$b^{1/2} = \left[\frac{1}{2} (1 - \beta) \right]^{1/2}$$

$$\eta = \frac{(1 - \beta^{1/2})}{\beta^{1/2}}$$

$$\delta(\%) = [(1 - \beta)/\beta] \times 100$$

In all of the present Nd^{III} complexes the positive and very small values of $b^{1/2}$ indicate poor covalency of the complexes. It is also supported by the calculated values of $\beta({}^4G_{5/2})$ (0.986 6–0.995 9) and $\beta({}^3P_{1/2})$ (0.998 2–0.999 5). Here the values of $\delta(\%)$ are found much below 1.5, which also suggests^{8,9} weak covalent bonding as well as weak metal–ligand interactions.

Ir spectra: On complexation, the blue-shift observed in $\nu_{\text{C=N}}$ of imine-nitrogen, symmetric and asymmetric ($\nu_{\text{C=C}} + \nu_{\text{C=N}}$) of pyridine ring as well as decrease in pyridine-ring-breathing modes clearly ascertain⁹ involvement of imine-N and pyridin-N in coordination, while a decrease in $\nu_{\text{C=S}}$ alongwith decrease in band intensity is indicative of metal–sulphur bond¹⁰. The strong bands observed at 610 and 595 cm^{-1} in the free ligand 'PFT' assigned¹¹ to ring-deformation modes, show red-shift of 15–25 cm^{-1} on complexation, indicating metal–ligand bond through furfuryl-oxygen. Strong bands observed at 640 and 572 cm^{-1} and medium bands at 490 and 471 cm^{-1} in free ligand 'PTT' possibly assigned¹¹ to thiophene (C=C) out-of-plane bending modes and (C–S–C) in-plane bending modes, respectively, also show red-shift of 20±5 cm^{-1} indicating involvement of thiophenyl sulphur on coordination. In all the present complexes, the medium and weak intensity bands observed in far-ir region at 523–507, 469–429, 331–317 and 281–270 cm^{-1} , tentatively assigned¹² to $\nu_{\text{M-imine-N}}$ ('PFT' and 'PTT' complexes only), $\nu_{\text{M-S}}$, $\nu_{\text{M-Py-N}}$ and $\nu_{\text{M-Cl}}$, respectively, also confirm the octahedral stereochemistry of the ligands 'PT', 'PFT' and 'PTT' around Nd^{III} ion as represented below.

Nd^{III} complex with 'PT'

Nd^{III} complexes² with
'PFT', where x=O
'PTT', where x=S
and $\alpha = \text{Cl}/\text{NO}_3/\text{ClO}_4$

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Lanthanide(III) Iodide Complexes of 5,6-Benzoquinoline and 2-Ethoxycarbonylaminopyridine

R. K. AGARWAL* and S. K. GUPTA

Department of Chemistry, Lajpat Rai Post-Graduate College,
Sahibabad-201 005

Manuscript received 5 November 1985, revised 21 July 1986,
accepted 5 September 1986

It is apparent that the ability of lanthanide ions to coordinate with neutral N-donors could best be evaluated in non-aqueous media, and a number of cationic or neutral complexes containing N-donor ligands have been isolated utilising non-aqueous media. In view of this, we report herein the coordinating ability of lanthanide(III) iodides with 5,6-benzoquinoline (Benzqn) and 2-ethoxycarbonylaminopyridine (ECAP). Lanthanide(III) perchlorate complexes of Benzqn are already known¹.

Experimental

The ligand 5,6-benzoquinoline (E.Merck) was used as such. The ligand 2-ethoxycarbonylaminopyridine was prepared² from 2-aminopyridine.

* 11/100, Rajendra Nagar, Sector 3, Sahibabad-201 005.